

Supplementary Materials

Medial Gastrocnemius (MG) activity during forwards perturbations

The below figure supplements the results described in the main manuscript for the medial gastrocnemius (MG) EMG response to the forward perturbations. As reported in the main manuscript, there were no statistically significant differences observed between nGVS and Sham with respect to MG activity in either the early (Sham, $Mean = 8.91\%$, $SD = 5.61$; nGVS, $Mean = 9.30\%$, $SD = 6.45$; $Z = -0.98$, $p = 0.326$, $r = 0.20$) or late epoch (Sham, $Mean = 11.50\%$, $SD = 7.08$; nGVS, $Mean = 12.25\%$, $SD = 8.19$; $Z = -1.84$, $p = 0.065$, $r = 0.37$). As noted, all p -values for this outcome are presented uncorrected given the exploratory nature of this analysis.

Supplementary Figure 1. A) Grand average plots of EMG amplitude of MG normalised to maximum voluntary contraction (%MVC) comparing nGVS condition (orange) to Sham (blue). Grand-average traces are for illustrative purposes only; iEMG analysis was conducted on a trial-by-trial basis. Boxplots with individual plotted paired data for early (B) and late (C) phase iEMG activity measured as amplitude normalised to maximum voluntary contraction (%MVC), $n = 25$.

Results from backwards perturbations

As with the primary analyses, 28 participants were used for the postural sway analyses and 25 used for the EMG analyses. Given the exploratory nature of these analyses, all p -values are presented uncorrected for multiple comparisons.

Postural Sway. As illustrated in the grand average plots (Supplementary Figure 2A), initial peak forward angular velocity tended to be reduced during nGVS (consistent with the primary analyses that focused on *backward* angular velocity elicited by forward perturbations). However, unlike the primary analyses, this difference was not statistically significant (Sham, $Mean = 12.63^\circ/\text{sec}$, $SD = 5.63$; nGVS, $Mean = 11.62^\circ/\text{sec}$, $SD = 4.76$; $Z = -1.16$; $p = 0.246$, $r = 0.22$; Supplementary Figure 2B).

Supplementary Figure 2. A) Postural sway defined by angular velocity (deg/s) of the trunk measured with a gyroscope at C7 is displaced as a grand average, comparing nGVS condition (orange) to Sham (blue). For illustrative purposes, positive values indicate forward angular velocity. Grand-average traces are shown for illustrative purposes; peak values were computed on a trial-by-trial basis prior to averaging to avoid temporal smearing. **B)** Boxplots with individual plotted paired data shows a non-significant reduction peak forward angular velocity (deg/s) in nGVS condition compared to sham ($n=28$).

EMG: MG. Consistent with the primary analyses of forward perturbations, no significant differences were observed between Sham and nGVS across any EMG outcomes during backward perturbations. Specifically, iEMG activity in the MG (the primary muscle responsible for arresting a forwards loss of balance) did not significantly differ between Sham and nGVS in either the early (Sham, Mean = 10.06%, SD = 7.06; nGVS, Mean = 9.74%, SD = 7.82; $Z = -0.39$, $p = 0.696$, $r = 0.08$; Supplementary Figure 3B) or late epoch (Sham, Mean = 11.53%, SD = 8.03; nGVS, Mean = 10.82%, SD = 7.18; $Z = -0.58$, $p = 0.563$, $r = 0.12$; Supplementary Figure 3C).

Supplementary Figure 3. A) Grand average plots of EMG amplitude of MG normalised to maximum voluntary contraction (%MVC) comparing nGVS condition (orange) to Sham (blue).

Grand-average traces are for illustrative purposes only; iEMG analysis was conducted on a trial-by-trial basis. Boxplots with individual plotted paired data for early (**B**) and late (**C**) phase iEMG activity measured as amplitude normalised to maximum voluntary contraction (%MVC), $n=25$.

EMG: TA. Likewise, tibialis anterior TA iEMG activity did not statistically differ between stimulation conditions in either the early (Sham, $Mean = 5.53\%$, $SD = 3.84$; nGVS, $Mean = 5.79\%$, $SD = 3.04$; $Z = -0.85$, $p = 0.397$, $r = 0.17$; Supplementary Figure 4B) or late epoch (Sham, $Mean = 7.04\%$, $SD = 5.30$; nGVS, $Mean = 6.66\%$, $SD = 3.52$; $Z = -0.71$, $p = 0.476$, $r = 0.14$; Supplementary Figure 4C).

Supplementary Figure 4. **A)** Grand average plots of EMG amplitude of TA normalised to maximum voluntary contraction (%MVC) comparing nGVS condition (orange) to Sham (blue). Grand-average traces are for illustrative purposes only; iEMG analysis was conducted on a trial-by-trial basis. Boxplots with individual plotted paired data for early (**B**) and late (**C**) phase iEMG activity measured as amplitude normalised to maximum voluntary contraction (%MVC), $n=25$.

Results from interlimb inter-muscular coherence (IMC)

There was a lack of observable differences in interlimb IMC for either the TA (Supplementary Figures 5A and B) or the MG muscle (Supplementary Figures 5C and D) during nGVS compared to Sham.

Supplementary Figure 5. Inter-limb (left-and-right leg) intermuscular coherence (IMC) for tibialis anterior (TA; **A and B**) and medial gastrocnemius (MG; **C and D**) between Sham (left panels) and nGVS conditions (right panels).